

DEVELOPMENT AND STANDARDIZATION OF A QUESTIONNAIRE TO MEASURE ICT-FAMILIARITY

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Abstract

This paper explains the procedure of developing and standardizing a questionnaire to measure ICT-Familiarity of college teachers. An exhaustive review of literature made it possible to decide upon the dimensions and areas which were concerned with ICT-Familiarity. Initially, 54 items were generated pertaining to the dimensions. Item total correlation between score of each item and score of total items were carried out by Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation 'r'. 28 items were retained which were significant at 0.05 level of significance. Scoring key was developed to score the questionnaire. Test-retest reliability was established for the questionnaire which is found 0.68. Questionnaire was validated against content validity adopted by Lawshe (1975). On the basis of NPC, norms were established on the scores of ICT-Familiarity questionnaire. The questionnaire to measure ICT-Familiarity developed and standardized by the researcher can be used to study the ICT-Familiarity of college teachers.

Introduction

Knowledge of modern technologies such as; computers, internet and projectors and skills required to use these tools is considered as ICT-Familiarity. It was found that integrating technology in the classroom, creates a rich, effective and efficient learning environment which improves students' performance and learning (Cronin et al. (1990), Frunckhourser (1993), George and sleeth (1996), Luna and Mekenzie (1997), Sheery et al. (2002), Trayner (2003). ICT should be combined with more traditional technologies, such as print and broadcast radio to achieve better effectiveness (Pelgram, Law 2003). ICT has a significant impact on teachers and teaching processes. ICT tools stimulate teachers. Teachers plan their lessons more efficiently. Finally, teachers become more convinced that educational achievements of the pupils are due to good ICT use. Parranton and Creed (2000) found that ICT is effective in raising teachers' capabilities, so it can be said that teachers should be ICT-Familiar. Martin and Dunsworth (2007) found that Word, PowerPoint, Excel and Internet, World Wide Web were highly rated as useful topics by both instructors and students. Dawson (2008) found that the most frequently used ICTs were; word-processing, e-mail, PowerPoint.

Need of the Study

Many attempts have been made to study and to measure computer attitude and computer aptitude but no efforts were put into develop the ICT-Familiarity Questionnaire and no measure were developed to quantify the ICT-Familiarity among college teachers. This necessitates the researcher to develop and to standardize an ICT-Familiarity Questionnaire. ICT-Familiarity Questionnaire is used to measure ICT-Familiarity of college teachers.

Objective

To develop and to standardize a self-reported questionnaire to assess ICT-Familiarity of college teachers.

Methodology

Normative survey method was used for the study.

Sample

For the present study, the data were collected from a sample of 350 college teachers using stratified random sampling technique.

Construction and Standardization of Questionnaire

Identification of Areas

An exhaustive review of literature made it possible to decide upon the dimensions and areas which were concerned with ICT-Familiarity of college teachers. After review of literature and discussions held by experts from relevant field, it was decided to retain five major areas- (a) Access and Use of ICT (b) Projectors (c) Computer (d) Internet Awareness (e) Internet Uses.

Preliminary Draft of Questionnaire

Initially, 54 items were generated pertaining to five areas- (a) Access and Use of ICT (b) Projectors (c) Computer (d) Internet Awareness (e) Internet Uses. This questionnaire is given to a group of 10 experts for their opinion and comments. 54 items were screened and 40 items were retained after excluding items with overlapping and preliminary draft of questionnaire was developed.

- **Pre-Tryout**

40 items were administered to a sample of 25 college teachers to check the language difficulties and to detect any ambiguity of items in the questionnaire. Minor changes were made in the language in some items as suggested by the college teachers.

- **Tryout**

Item total correlation between score of each item and score of total items were carried out by using Karl Person's coefficient of correlation, 'r'. Correlation coefficient computed on the scores of 50 college teachers. After item total correlation, 28 items were retained which were significant at 0.05 level of significance, 12 items were eliminated since they were not significant even at 0.05 level of significance. 28 items were finalized in the questionnaire.

- **Scoring**

Scoring-key was developed by the researcher to score the questionnaire. Four options were given in each items. Scores vary from 28 to 112 from minimum to maximum range.

- **Reliability**

The final version of the questionnaire was administered to 120 college teachers. The test-retest reliability was established for the questionnaire by computing the coefficient of correlation between two sets of scores of same individuals on ICT-Familiarity Questionnaire at different intervals after 15 days. The test retest reliability of ICT-Familiarity Questionnaire was found 0.68.

- **Validity**

Content validity was established by the method adopted by Lawshe (1975). The list of 28 items is given to twelve experts from ICT area to rate how relevant the items were to measure ICT-Familiarity of college teachers. content validity ratio (CVR) was computed. When 12 SMEs (Subject Matter Experts) rate the items of the questionnaire, at least 0.56 would be required to retain the item in the questionnaire. It can be concluded that all the items have CVR more than 0.56, So all the 28 items are retained in the questionnaire.

- **Norms**

These scores were obtained from 350 college teachers. Teachers who scored above 106 are considered ICT-High Familiar, teachers who scored from 81 to 105 are considered ICI - Moderate Familiar, teachers who scored from 56 to 80 are considered, ICT-Low Familiar and teachers who scored from 32 to 55 are considered ICT-Unfamiliar.

Conclusion

The ICT-Familiarity Questionnaire is developed and standardized by the researcher. Questionnaire can be used to study the ICT-Familiarity of college teachers.

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